

Oil Slicks

How can SAR detect oil slicks?

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In this Story Map we will show how Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images can be used to detect oil slicks. The capabilities presented here are focused on L-band radars such as NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR Mission).

Background

Every year, emergency responders work to prevent hundreds of oil and chemical spills from harming people and the environment. Rapid identification of spilled oil in the vast open waters of the oceans and gulf is key to minimizing damage, especially as spills that occur far from the coast aren't generally monitored or mitigated. Radar remote sensing plays a crucial role in providing the necessary information for efficient detection and response to oil spills and can also be used to monitor shipping routes for illegal dumping (see [NISAR White Paper](#)).

Questions of interest after an oil spill include: where is the oil? How much oil is there? What is the oil's trajectory? SAR can be used to help discriminate oil from the clean sea surface and detect the presence, thickness, and movement of oil.

NASA's C-20A UAVSAR Surveys Gulf Oil Spill Area

NASA/NOAA Tech Will Aid Marine Oil Spill Response

How to interpret oil slicks with SAR?

SAR sensors send microwave pulses and record the strength of the signal reflected off the ground and back to the sensor, also referred to as the backscatter. By convention, SAR images are displayed in grayscale with bright areas indicating stronger detected signal or high backscatter and darker areas indicating low backscatter.

In SAR images, oil slicks appear as darker areas compared to the surrounding water surface. The oil suppresses the ocean's capillary waves or dampens the ocean's surface roughness. Smoother surfaces return less signal to the satellite, and as a result, oil slicks have lower radar backscatter relative to the surrounding ocean.

The figure below shows a radar image of the Deep Horizon Oil Spill on June 23, 2010. In the radar image, the oil slick appears darker compared to the surrounding ocean.

Source: <https://www.flickr.com/photos/skytruth/4733142029/in/photostream/>

The figure to the left shows the estimated oil spill extent in red for June 23, 2010, provided by NOAA and derived from

Source: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/1-Analysis-Deepwater-Horizon-L-band-UAVSAR-data-AR-data.pdf>

various satellite sources. Notice how the estimated slick extent corresponds with these darker regions.

The case study below explores a specific region of the Deepwater Horizon oil slick.

Case Studies

Gulf Coast Deep Horizon Oil Spill

The Deep Horizon Oil Spill released 4 million barrels of oil into the Gulf of Mexico between April 20, 2010 and July 15, 2010. The Uninhabited Aerial Vehicle Synthetic Aperture Radar (UAVSAR) L-band SAR was deployed to the Gulf of Mexico from June 22–23, 2010, to collect data for scientific studies of the main oil slick and the extent and impact of oil on coastal marshlands. NASA JPL's UAVSAR is an L-Band airborne radar and NISAR testbed instrument.

SAR image of the Deepwater Horizon oil spill (June 23, 2010). Source: <https://www.nasa.gov/topics/earth/features/uavsar20121025i.html>

The left SAR backscatter image showcases the oil slick as a darker feature than the surrounding ocean. Since the oil slick is smooth, less energy, or backscatter, returns to the radar instrument. The radar data is then classified into the colorful insets, which show thicker, concentrated emulsions in red/yellow and minimal oil contamination in green/blue. Dark blue indicates clear ocean water surrounding the oil slick.

In the figure below, the oil slick is differentiated from the surrounding water in dark blue. Within the oil slick, the color images can also help differentiate different oil characteristics and features.

Source: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/1-Analysis-Deepwater-Horizon-L-band-UAVSAR-data-AR-data.pdf>

North Sea Oil Experiment

The Norwegian Clean Seas Association for Operating Companies or NOFO conducts oil spill cleanup simulations in the North Sea. In June 2015, UAVSAR flew over the oil-slicked area during the simulation to detect the presence and depth of oil.

For the simulation, three emulsions, or mixtures of oil and water, were released with varying oil content, or 40% (E40), 60% (E60), and 80% (E80). The other release was plant oil or (P) to simulate a natural biogenic slick (Skrunes et al. 2016).

Note these different oil slicks in the UAVSAR acquisitions below and observe their differences in movement.

Image Credit: NOFO

<https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/nasa-joins-north-sea-oil-cleanup-training-exercise>

HIGH**LOW**

Radar backscatter in the HH polarization

UAVSAR acquisitions of the NOFO simulation. See oil slicks changing and moving over time.

SAR vs. Optical Imagery

SAR can offer data coverage during cloudy conditions or when optical sensors are unavailable. Below is an example from [Garcia-Pineda et al. 2015](#) showing an Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) L-Band SAR image and MERIS RGB optical image in the lower right, both collected on May 24, 2010. The oil slicks appear dark in the SAR image. Because of sunglint, in optical imagery oil slicks can appear either brighter or darker than the nearby water, depending on the viewing geometry.

Example oil slick from [Garcia-Pineda et al. 2015](#) showing ALOS L-Band SAR image and MERIS RGB optical image in the lower right.

Technology

Why SAR?

Credit: NASA SAR Handbook

Synthetic Aperture Radars (SARs) transmit microwave pulses and receive the echoes that backscatter from the Earth's surface. The amount of signal that is backscattered depends upon the properties of the objects on the surface. This backscatter information can be transformed into high-resolution radar remote-sensing products with detailed information

about surface characteristics. Unlike optical sensors, SAR is an active sensor that can be employed to delineate oil slick extent at night or during cloud cover. This is particularly useful with oil spills, as the location and extent of the slick may change

significantly day to day, requiring a sensor that can detect extent regardless of cloud cover and time of day.

NISAR (NASA-ISRO SAR) is an upcoming radar instrument collecting data in the L-band wavelength (23.8 cm). NISAR will provide high-resolution, near-global, and continual mapping of Earth's natural resources and hazards, such as oil slicks. Explore the NISAR Sample Data Product Suite, or planned NISAR data products and their product specifications, here: <https://nisar.jpl.nasa.gov/data/sample-data/>

Radar Scattering and Polarizations

Radar data is collected at different polarizations, or combinations of horizontal and vertical radar waves (i.e. HH, HV, etc.). Each polarization is a separate data product generated by the radar, and the different polarizations have unique interactions with the surface targets.

For example, the images shown in this Story Map are HH, which denotes a horizontally emitted, horizontally collected wave. The VV (vertically emitted, vertically collected)

polarization is more commonly used for oil spill applications due to its higher return power, but only HH and HV polarizations will be available from NISAR for the ocean and coastal waters.

The expected scattering mechanisms in an oil slick area are described below:

- **Surface Scattering:** occurs when there is a smooth surface, such as oil on open water. In specular scattering, the signal

Credit: NASA SAR Handbook

Credit: Cathleen Jones

scatters away from the radar, and as a result, oil slicks on open water appear dark in the image.

- **Rough Scattering:** can occur where some, but not all, of the signal scatters away from the radar. This could be due to wind roughening on open water or areas of shorter vegetation.

References and Further Reading

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